

Spectrophotometric Study of the Reaction of Promazine Hydrochloride with Palladium(II), Osmium(VIII) and Osmium(VI)

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Promazine hydrochloride (PMH) forms a red coloured complex with Pd(II) in acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer of pH 4.5-5.5 and a red coloured radical cation with Os(VIII) or Os(VI) in 1-3 M hydrochloric acid medium. The palladium-PMH complex and the radical cation exhibit maximum absorption at 498 and 515 nm, respectively. The composition of the Pd(II)-PMH complex is 1 : 1. The apparent stability constant of the complex at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 , $27 \pm 1^\circ$ has a log K value of 5.9 ± 0.1 . The proposed methods offer the advantages of simplicity, stability, rapidity and sensitivity without the need for an extraction step or heating the solution.

PROMAZINE hydrochloride (PMH), 10-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]phenothiazine hydrochloride, was proposed as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of ruthenium(III)¹, cerium(IV)² and gold(III)³. A survey of literature shows that no attempt has been made to use PMH as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of palladium(II), osmium(VIII) and osmium(VI). The present investigation deals with the study of the colour reaction of PMH with palladium(II), osmium(VIII) and osmium(VI) for spectrophotometric determination of palladium and osmium.

Experimental

Beckman spectrophotometer, model DB with matched 1 cm silica cells was used for absorbance measurements. The pH of the solutions was measured (vs SCE) with a pH meter, model L1-10 (M/S Electronic and Industrial Instruments, Hyderabad, India).

A stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared by dissolving 0.3402 g palladium(II) chloride (Johnson Matthey) in 500 ml 0.1 M hydrochloric acid and standardised gravimetrically by the dimethylglyoxime method⁴.

A stock solution of osmium(VIII) was prepared from osmium tetroxide (Johnson Matthey) and standardised⁵.

A stock solution of Os(VI) was prepared from potassium osmate (Johnson Matthey) in double distilled water and standardised⁶.

A 0.2% solution of PMH was prepared in double distilled water and stored in an amber bottle in a refrigerator.

Walpole buffer solutions⁷ and solutions of diverse ions were prepared using analytical grade reagents.

Procedure for the determination of palladium(II) :

An aliquot of the sample solution containing 5-237.5 μ g palladium was transferred to a 25 ml calibrated volumetric flask. 5 ml acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer of pH 5.0 and 5 ml 0.2% PMH solution were added and diluted to the mark with double distilled water. The solutions were thoroughly mixed and the absorbance was measured at 498 nm against a corresponding reagent blank prepared in the same manner. The concentration of Pd(II) in the sample solution was deduced from a standard calibration curve.

Procedure for the determination of osmium(VIII) and osmium(VI) :

To an aliquot of the sample solution containing 6.25-187.5 μ g Os(VIII) or 6.25-200 μ g Os(VI) were added 10 ml 5 M hydrochloric acid and 4 ml 0.2% PMH solution and the volume made up to 25 ml with double distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 515 nm against a reagent blank prepared similarly. The amount of Os(VIII) or Os(VI) was deduced from a standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Determination of Pd(II) :

PMH reacts with palladium(II) instantaneously to form a red coloured complex at room temperature (27°) in hydrochloric acid, hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate or acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer medium. The sensitivity and the stability of the complex depend on the nature of the medium. The sensitivity of the reaction in hydrochloric acid (pH 0.0-1.5) or in hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate (pH 2.1-3.7) medium is less than that in acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. The stability of the complex

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in hydrochloric acid, hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate and acetic acid-sodium acetate medium is 1.5, 6 and 24 hr, respectively. Acetic acid-sodium acetate medium has therefore been selected for further studies because of higher sensitivity and stability of the complex and less interference of many foreign ions.

The effective pH range where reproducible results are obtained is 4.5-5.5 as shown by the constancy of λ_{\max} . Below and above this pH range, the maximum intensity of the colour of the complex is not obtained. The palladium-PMH complex exhibits maximum absorbance at 492-508 nm where palladium(II) and the reagent do not absorb appreciably.

The effect of reagent concentration was examined by measuring the absorbance at 498 nm of solutions containing a known concentration of palladium and varying amounts of the reagent. A sixteen fold molar excess of the reagent over palladium(II) is required to obtain maximum absorbance. The effect of varying temperature on the stability of the complex was investigated. The absorbance readings are constant in the temperature range 8-90°.

Calibration, range and sensitivity :

The Pd-PMH complex obeys Beer's law over the concentration range 0.2-9.5 ppm. The optimum concentration range for effective spectrophotometric determination as evaluated by Ringbom's curve^{9,10} is 0.8-9.0 ppm. The sensitivity of the reaction as calculated from Beer's law plot is 11 ng/cm² with molar absorptivity of 9.61×10^4 l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 498 nm. The mean absorbance studied for 10 different samples each containing a final Pd(II) concentration of 4 ppm has been found to be 0.37 with a standard deviation of 0.0015. The accuracy of the method is $\pm 2\%$. It has been found that there is no appreciable change in the absorbance or in colour intensity of the complex if the order of addition of the reagents was changed.

Composition of the palladium-PMH complex :

Continuous variations^{10,11} and mole ratio¹² methods were employed to establish the composition of the complex. The determinations were made in a medium of constant ionic strength (0.1 M sodium nitrate) at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 and $27 \pm 1^\circ$. The absorbances of the solutions were measured at 498 nm. The results indicated the formation of a 1 : 1 complex between the metal and the reagent.

The apparent stability constant of the complex was calculated from absorbance data by the mole ratio method. The log K value obtained for the complex is 5.9 ± 0.1 .

The electrolytic nature of the complex was found by ion-exchange experiments. When 25 ml 10^{-5} M solution of the complex was passed through Dowex 50W - X8 cation exchange resin column (30 × 1.4 cm) the red colour was completely absorbed and the eluent was colourless. When Dowex 1-X8 anion exchange resin column was used, the eluent was red

coloured. This indicated that the complex was cationic.

In order to assess the possible analytical application of the reaction, the effects of some ions which often accompany Pd(II) were studied. For these studies, different amounts of the ionic species were added to 100 μ g Pd(II) solution contained in 25 ml volumetric flasks and the colour was developed as outlined in the standard procedure. The following amounts (μ g/ml) of foreign ions were found to give less than 2% error in the determination of 4 μ g/ml Pd(II) : Os(VIII) 6 ; Pt(IV), Rh(III) 12 ; Ru(III) 5 ; Au(III) 0.2 ; Ir(III) 12 ; Fe(III) 1.0 ; Sb(III) 50 ; Cu(II) 250 ; Co(II) 180 ; Ni(II), UO₂(II) 210 ; Ce(IV) 0.10 ; fluoride 2000 ; chloride 7000 ; bromide 150 ; iodide 0.30 ; nitrate 2500 ; sulphate 4000 ; phosphate 1000 ; oxalate 250 ; acetate 1200 ; thiosulphate 0.1 ; tartrate 1500 ; citrate 2000 and EDTA 0.20.

Determination of Os(VIII) and Os(VI) :

PMH forms a red coloured species with Os(VIII) or Os(VI) in presence of hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric or acetic acid. It does not react with osmium(IV). The red coloured species is thought to be a radical cation¹³. The maximum colour development takes place instantaneously at room temperature (27°). The sensitivity and the stability of the red coloured species depend on the nature and concentration of the acid medium. The sensitivity of the reaction in four acid media is in the order HCl > H₂SO₄ \approx H₃PO₄ > HAc. The stability of the red species in 1.5 M solution of HCl, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄ and HAc is 60, 40, 40 and 10 min, respectively. Hence, hydrochloric acid medium is recommended. Nitric acid medium cannot be used as it oxidises PMH to a red coloured product.

The absorption maximum of the red species is at 510-520 nm where the reagent does not absorb, thus promoting excellent analytical applications. The maximum absorbance readings are obtained in 1-3 M hydrochloric acid medium. Below 1 M HCl the absorbance is low and above 3 M the reagent slowly undergoes oxidation. An eleven fold molar excess of the reagent over Os(VIII) or Os(VI) is required to obtain the maximum absorbance. The absorbance values are constant in the temperature range 8-50°. The order of addition of the reagents is of no consequence.

Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.25-7.5 ppm Os(VIII) or 0.25-8.0 ppm Os(VI). The optimum range for accurate determination of Os as evaluated by Ringbom plot^{7,8} is 0.63-7.1 ppm Os(VIII) or 0.63-7.5 ppm Os(VI). The molar absorptivity is 2.4×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for Os(VIII) and 1.8×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for Os(VI). According to Sandell's expression, the sensitivity of the reaction is 7 ng/cm² for Os(VIII) and 9.2 ng/cm² for Os(VI). Sample solutions containing 6 ppm of Os(VIII) [Os(VI)] give a mean absorbance of 0.745 [(0.47)] with a standard deviation of 0.0018 [(0.022)]. The accuracy of the determinations is $\pm 2\%$.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM AND OSMIUM IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CORRESPONDING TO ALLOYS AND MINERALS

Mixture	Metal taken ppm		Metal ion added ppm						Metal found ^a ppm	
	Pd	Os	Ru	Ir	Pt	Rh	Au	Sb	Pd	Os
Jewellery alloy	1.0	—	0.046	—	—	—	—	—	1.01	—
	2.5	—	0.115	—	—	—	—	—	2.53	—
	3.0	—	0.138	—	—	—	—	—	3.03	—
	3.5	—	0.161	—	—	—	—	—	3.46	—
	4.0	—	0.184	—	—	—	—	—	4.01	—
Stibiopalladinite mineral	0.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.165	0.49	—
	1.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.330	0.99	—
	2.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.660	2.03	—
	3.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.990	2.96	—
	4.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.320	4.02	—
Syserkite mineral	—	2.0	0.32	1.6	0.076	0.002	0.002	—	—	1.99
	—	2.5	0.40	2.0	0.095	0.0025	0.0025	—	—	2.51
	—	3.0	0.48	2.4	0.114	0.0030	0.0030	—	—	3.01
	—	3.5	0.56	2.8	0.133	0.0035	0.0035	—	—	3.49
	—	4.0	0.64	3.2	0.152	0.0040	0.0040	—	—	3.99
	—	5.0	0.80	4.0	0.190	0.0050	0.0050	—	—	5.02

* Average of five determinations.

The following amounts ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of foreign ions which commonly accompany Os(VIII) or Os(VI) were found to give less than 2% error in the determination of 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Os(VIII) or Os(VI): Pt(IV) 6; Rh(III) 20; Ru(III) 1.5; Ir(III) 16; Pd(II) 0.5; Au(III) 0.6; Cu(II) 200; Ni(II) 480; Co(II) 640; Fe(III) 1.0; UO_2 (II) 1200; V(V) 0.8; Ce(IV) 0.5; Mn(II) 700; fluoride 4544; chloride 4854; bromide 1000; iodide 1.5; nitrate 12000; sulphate 5000; phosphate 3600; oxalate 1000; acetate 6210; citrate 6000; tartrate 6600; thiosulphate 1.2 and EDTA 0.6.

Applications :

Determination of palladium and osmium in synthetic mixtures corresponding to the composition of jewellery alloy, stibiopalladinite and syserkite minerals :

Analysed samples of jewellery alloy (Pd, 95.5; Ru, 4.5%), stibiopalladinite mineral (Pd, 75; Sb, 25%) and syserkite mineral (Os, 50; Ir, 40; Ru, 8; Rh, 0.05; Au, 0.05%) were not available. Hence synthetic mixtures containing the metal ions corresponding to the composition of the alloy and the minerals were prepared. The palladium and osmium contents were determined following the standard procedures. The results given in Table 1 show that the proposed methods can be used successfully for the determination of palladium in jewellery alloy and stibiopalladinite mineral and osmium in syserkite mineral.

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